

Chenab Bridge in Jammu and Kashmir a Massive Structure in Making

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Abstract— Chenab is a major River flowing through Jammu and Kashmir on which Indian Railways constructed a massive bridge structure known as Chenab Bridge located in Reasi district. The bridge having a height of 359 m (Deck Height) above the river was completed in August 2022 and the track laying work on the bridge was completed in March 2023. This massive bridge structure is scheduled to drive the facility in 2024. Construction of Chenab Bridge has been declared as the World's highest railway bridge. The bridge has a total length of 1315 m with 17 spans including a trussed arch main span of length 469 m. The arch is being constructed with the help of two self-propelled auxiliary cable cranes, moving along cables spanning between 100m-high temporary pylons at each side of the valley. This Study will describe the design and engineering of the bridge. The massive Construction of a bridge has many design challenges such as the erection of the steel arch by cable crane, the huge dimensions of the bridge, and its special design desires the earthquake and blast load effects. The challenges in the design erection and overall Construction of the bridge is being studied. The Bridge has connected the Valley of Kashmir to the rest of India and will surely boost the region's different sectors by providing all-weather rail connectivity.

Keywords— Construction, Chenab Bridge, Structure, Railways.

I. INTRODUCTION

Kashmir Valley which is surrounded by the mighty mountains, located at an altitude of about 1620 m above MSL, with a spread of 135 km x 32 km, is matchless in numerous ways. The valley is endowed with natural springs and dense Forests and has an abundance of fruit orchards. It is a tourist paradise known as paradise on Earth and India is commissioning one of its most challenging railway projects perpetually by connecting the Kashmir valley to the rest of India through the Himalayan slopes. The USBRL project will play an immense role in the future development of Jammu and Kashmir in Particular. The survey of this Rail line from Udhampur to Srinagar was conducted first time in 1997. The Construction of the USBRL (Udhampur Srinagar Baramulla Rail Link) Project is still ongoing. In Kashmir Valley, the trains are running between Banihal & Baramulla while crossing one of the longest railway tunnels in the World. The Chenab Bridge is situated in the most difficult portion of the Jammu-Udhampur-Srinagar Baramulla rail route, which is characterized by young Himalayan rock. Broken rock with dolomitic limestone and firestone lentils with a silicate concentration make up the topography. Rock formations exposed between Jammu and Qazigund are crossed by three major thrusts besides several local thrusts, shear zones, and faults. There are rocks of class 3 to 5 with a strength of 60 to 100 MPa and a volume weight of 2.7 t/m³. The rock mass rating is a measure of the amount of rock in a certain area. [1, 2] Situated in a tremendously severe mountainous area with diffident roads and infrastructure conditions, the construction of the bridge has been greatly inspiring and challenging.

II. NEED OF THE USBRL PROJECT TO BE UNDERTAKEN:

Due to the strategic location of Jammu and Kashmir, The connectivity to this state is right important for general security and overall development. Even though it had plenty of resources the Union Territory could not make necessary development reason being its poor connectivity to the rest of India. And at present Exertions are on for the beginning of rail connectivity to the region for which many railway projects has been commenced which are under construction in different phases. Considering the topography of the region the rail projects are much challenging. The USBRL project has been declared as a National Project and the Institutions like Indian Institute of Delhi, Indian Institute of Roorkee, GSI (Geographical Survey of India) and DRDO are providing proficiency and expertise in the project planning, operation and Implementation.

The completion of the project will mark the all-weather connectivity of the valley to the rest of India and will provide a mass transportation with cost effectiveness and hence will play a major role in the development works. It can also play an important role in quick industrialization, transportation of raw materials and final products from Jammu & Kashmir and hence will encourage the trade and tourism in the valley apart from providing openings for employment. Likewise it will be a bonus for development of agriculture, horticulture and floriculture sectors of this area.

III. MAIN FEATURES AND TECHNICAL CHALLENGES:

Chenab Bridge a massive structure lies between 33.15° N and 74.88° E the Bridge has a length of 1,315m and built at a height of 359m or 1,178 ft above the river. The maximum height of the pier as 133.7m, it includes 17 spans and the Arch span of 485m or 1532 feet. It includes a 14m-wide dual carriageway and a 1.2m-wide central verge. The Chenab Bridge will have a lifespan of 120 years. The construction process considered the aesthetic worth of the bridge and prepared a strong effort to fetch a natural tempo to the spot. The design of the bridge in the context of a structural view is associated with many challenges. The extra significant aspect of the Chenab bridge construction to support the bridge is building stable rock slopes in a robust terrain. And number of stabilization techniques, i.e. grouting, slope, use of rock bolts, flattening, and drainage have been designed to minimize the possibility of failures for the slope. The slope stabilization using active prestressed rock anchors and passive rock bolts has been used against wedge failure [3]. The Bridge is being designed as a huge steel arch one of its first kind in India. The deck of the Chenab Bridge is positioned on a transition curve with a changing radius and Construction was therefore carried out in phases resulting a gradual change in the alignment. And it is the first time that a bridge was constructed incrementally on a transition curve. The use of Cable cranes and derricks was done to construct the bridge. The cable cranes employed for the project were one of the biggest in the world [4]. The Construction of the Chenab Bridge required $46,000\text{m}^3$ of concrete 25,000t of steel and 4,000t of reinforced steel, and the excavation of eight million cubic meters. To resist the encounter of aggressive weather, the steel being used shall resist temperatures as low as -20C and wind speeds of 200 kmph. Apart from natural forces the engineers also face the challenge of construction in one of the greatest complicated isolated and inaccessible terrains, while also ensuring that the movement of the river is not disturbed.

Considering the challenges the transportation of the men, material and machinery to the location was much more difficult second at such a highly active seismic area it was a high challenge to consider the massive bridge structure against the seismic activities in the area where around 263 earthquakes have struck within 300 km of Jammu and Kashmir from last 10 years with a magnitude of 4 or above. While considering the seismicity and seismotectonics the site area possesses a moderate to strong risk of earthquakes [5]. The constructed bridge is located in zone IV, which is classified as a severe intensity zone. However, as a precautionary measure against earthquakes, it has been designed to withstand forces of zone V, which is the highest intensity earthquake zone. It is worth noting that zone II represents the lowest intensity zone. The Chenab Bridge has been engineered to easily withstand an earthquake with a magnitude of 8.0. When calculating the earthquake loading, two types of loading need to be considered: the maximum considered earthquake (MCE) and the design basis earthquake (DBE). For the Chenab Bridge, the maximum ground acceleration for MCE can be assumed as 0.31 g, while the corresponding value for DBE is required to be 0.16 g.

Considering the wind engineering the size of the bridge was not the major challenge but the altitude and the site location. Hence a special type of wind tunnel testing was therefore conducted to assess the design wind parameters. Wind engineering of the bridge was conducted by combining in-house wind engineering expertise and the wind tunnel tests of FORCE Technology in Denmark. The first test involved a large-size topography model of the bridge site. It revealed some unusual wind characteristics, including up to 11 degrees vertical inclination of the mean wind velocity and wide scatter of turbulence intensity from 7 percent to 55 percent, depending on wind direction. The next test in the program was standard section model testing, which contributed updated aerodynamic input to WSP's advanced 3D buffeting analysis and equivalent static wind load extraction.[6] The facility wind load relates to a greatest breeze pressing factor of 1500 Pa and The breeze load is overseeing the curve plan [7]. The extension is envisioned to face the wind velocities up to 260km/h.

IV. COMPONENT PARTS:

The substructure of Bridge includes the Foundation, Piers and Bearings while in Superstructure Pylons, Arch Foundation completes the massive structure. For the foundations the open foundation of the bridge has been proposed and to avoid the edges from waterline, a single main span of 160 m with two end spans of 60m each has been chosen. The piers consisting of the hollow rectangular section on a raft foundation with the outer dimensions of 6.6 m x 5 m. As there is curvature in the track of the bridge hence the bearings are made in such a way that the segment becomes easier. In the Superstructure plate girder in the form of main superstructure portion with a close deck. The closed-deck provides a dry environment keeping the rainwater out. Girder helps to connect the rail. Deck wind noses are designed in the main arch portion [8]. In Superstructure the height of the pylons is approximately 105m and 127m at the end of Bakkal and Kauri respectively. This steel structure has used to make the arch section of the bridge. A cable crane has been built with 34 ton lifting capacity to construct the steel structure. Both sides of the valley are associated with the pylon towers. The same helps the cable cranes to move in between the pylon towers. [9]. the arch section of this iconic bridge is entirely made of steel. The main arch foundation is about 47m at the Bakkal end and 34m at the Kauri end. Initially, pipe segments were used for each individual's member of the through truss. Later, the diagonal members and chords of the trusses were sealed steel boxes, primarily for on-site production. The alternative members were kept as circular. The concrete filling has improved the stiffness and the damping ratio. The same has been done for the members of chord to control the wind forces. The superstructure of the main arch portion is supported by steel piers. The client preferred the steel arch concept. Several steel arch alternatives as well as the idea of a cable-stayed bridge were investigated during the tender period. The Anjikhad Bridge, another steel arch bridge, constructed on the railway track. It adheres to a comparable idea at a The Chenab Bridge's arch and arch piers were constructed using substantial steel trusses. The original plan was to employ pipe sections for each component of the arch to minimize wind resistance. Later on, the diagonals and chords of the trusses were changed to become sealed steel boxes to make production easier on-site. The secondary members and all other members were kept in the loop.

The steel work for the bridge will be carried out at workshops set up in the mountains. Due to the lack of a proper road network in the challenge area, the workshops have been moved to the construction site. The longest building arts that can be delivered to the site are 12 meters in length. In the mountains, four workshops have been constructed. Workshops and paint shops built next to them are located on both sides of the valley. All steel materials, except for the smallest rolled profiles, are delivered to the mountains as steel boards. Other challenges arise due to the lack of infrastructure in this area. There's no electricity, and the water of the river isn't suitable for concrete production. At the site, all electricity and water must be produced. It was delivered from far away in the mountains. It's also a difficult job because of the curve in the track on the approach bridge. In this section, we're going to cover: To allow the steel deck to be launched, the construction stage bearings have been designed in such a way that they can be launched. When the next arch pier location is reached, temporary cables will be installed to support the arch, and the new arch pier will be constructed on the free end. The superstructure can then be supported by the arch pier and so forth until the last arch pier is reached. The deck of the bridge will be welded in the workshop upside down in about 8-meter-long sections because the welding points in the final structure are mainly located under the bridge. Once the work has been completed, the sections are turned around and delivered to the next stage of the process. Several additional parameters such as fatigue, global stability, second-order effects, and composite action are required for the design of the main arch. It also requires that the bridge is designed for a consistent level of reliability in all load cases, as well as to meet construction standards. In the current design work, it has also been taken into account. The Chenab Bridge will be the biggest / the longest-span / the highest railway arch bridge ever built in the world. Its design presented

great challenges for the team, but it will become even more difficult to close the gap in the main arch's sides before they are complete.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The bridge has been designed in such a way as to be able to achieve uniform reliability. It has been applied for all load cases and needs to be compatible with the design and construction standards. In the present design work, it has also been used. Once the bridge is open to run a train on it, it may be declared the highest rail bridge in the world. The design team is faced with a major task, but the main arches are full and it takes time. Due to the bridge, Jammu & Kashmir is about to enter a new era. The construction of an access road due to improved conditions and Infrastructure, increased opportunities for employment for the youth as well.

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